

A Study on Complex Formation of Beryllium with Salicylic and Sulphosalicylic Acids. Part II

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The complexes formed by salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids with beryllium have been studied by spectrophotometry. The stability constants have been determined at pH 4.0 and at different ionic strengths. ΔH and ΔS of the formation of the complexes have been calculated from the temperature coefficients of the stability constants.

In an earlier communication¹, we have studied the complexes formed by salicylic and sulphosalicylic acids with beryllium at pH 4.5. In the present communication we report further results on the same systems at another pH (4.0) with a view to ascertaining the influence of hydrogen-ion concentration on the stability of these complexes. Besides, the thermodynamic functions, ΔH and ΔS , of the reactions have been determined from the temperature coefficients of the stability constants.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details were the same as in our previous communication¹. The extinction coefficients of the complexes and the ligands were determined in the same way as in the previous part¹. The values for the extinction coefficients of Be(II)-salicylic acid and Be(II)-sulphosalicylic acid complexes at pH 4.0 and wave length 315 m μ were found to be 3856 (± 12) and 3753 (± 12) respectively against 1201 (± 4) and 1030 (± 4) respectively for the corresponding ligands.

DISCUSSION

The stability constants,

$$K = \frac{[\text{Complex}]}{\{[\text{Be}^{2+}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{complex}]\} \{[\text{ligand}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{complex}]\}}$$

have been determined for both the complexes at pH 4.0 and at different ionic strengths (0.02, 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2). Table I records the values of the stability constants determined for both the complexes.

As expected, the stability constant decreases with an increase in the ionic strengths of the solutions.

1. Das and Aditya, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 19.

TABLE I

*Stability constants of the complexes.*Wave length = 315 m μ . Cell width = 1 cm. pH = 4.0.

Ionic strength.	A. Be—S.S.A. complex (at 29.5°).		B. Be—S.A. complex (at 29°).	
	No. of readings taken with diff. cond.	$K_{AV} \times 10^{-4}$.	No of readings taken with diff. cond.	$K_{AV} \times 10^{-4}$.
0.02	8	0.765 (± 0.010)	8	0.452 (± 0.014)
0.05	9	0.540 (± 0.020)	8	0.368 (± 0.010)
0.10	8	0.465 (± 0.011)	9	0.337 (± 0.009)
0.20	9	0.378 (± 0.017)	8	0.303 (± 0.004)

TABLE II

pH.	$K [H^+] \text{ at } \mu =$				$K [H^+] \text{ at } \mu =$			
	0.02.	0.05.	0.1.	0.2.	0.02.	0.05.	0.1.	0.2.
	A. Be—S. S. A. complex.				B. Be.—S. A. complex.			
4.0	0.765	0.540	0.465	0.378	0.452	0.368	0.337	0.303
4.5	0.704	0.542	0.475	0.465	0.381	0.319	0.296	0.285

A comparison of the stability constants at the corresponding ionic strengths at pH 4.0 and 4.5 (reported earlier¹) show that these are clearly different. Incorporation of $[H^+]$ at its first power in the numerator provides values of ' K' ', which are recorded in Table II.

The agreements between the values are good, considering the experimental limitations. This can be explained on the basis of the equilibrium as:

where HR stands for

For the sake of simplicity, charges on different species are omitted.

Entropy and Enthalpy Changes.—Because of the uncertainties in obtaining the stability constant at the zero-ionic strength by the extrapolation method, we have determined the constants in media with a fixed ionic strength of 0.2 at two different temperatures in addition to that at the room temperature for the calculations of ΔH and ΔS . As such, our values of ΔH and ΔS are for medium with an ionic strength of 0.2. Table III records the results.

Assuming ΔH 's for the formation of each complex to be constant over the experimental range of temperature, the changes in enthalpy of formation have been calculated from the slopes of the plots of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 1 and 2).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

TABLE III

Ionic strength = 0.2. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Temp.	No. of readings with diff. conc.	$K_{AV} \times 10^{-4}$.	Temp.	No. of readings with diff. conc.	$K_{AV} \times 10^{-4}$.
A. Be-S. S. A. complex.			B. Be-S. A. complex.		
20°	9	0.356 (± 0.017)	20°	8	0.280 (± 0.005)
29.5°	9	0.376 (± 0.017)	29°	8	0.303 (± 0.004)
45°	9	0.427 (± 0.020)	40°	8	0.334 (± 0.005)

ΔF 's and ΔH 's being known, ΔS 's for the reactions have been calculated from the relationship: $\Delta F = \Delta H - T\Delta S$. Table IV records the free energy, entropy, and enthalpy changes for the formation reactions for both the complexes at 25°.

TABLE IV

Reaction: $\text{Be} + \text{HR} \rightleftharpoons \text{BeR} + \text{H}^+$ (charges omitted).

$$K = \frac{[\text{BeR}]}{[\text{Be}][\text{HR}]} \text{ at } \text{pH} = 4.0, \mu = 0.2 \text{ and } 25^\circ$$

Complex.	ΔF (kcal.).	ΔH (kcal.).	ΔS (e.u.).
Be-S.S.A	-4.86 (± 0.03)	1.40 (± 0.15)	21.0 (± 1.4)
Be-S.A	-4.73 (± 0.01)	1.67 (± 0.15)	21.5 (± 1.0)

Comparison with other data.—It will be interesting to compare our results with the results obtained by other workers. A comparison of our results with that of Meek and Banks² is not possible as they worked at a pH range of 9-11 where 1:2 complex exists in solution, whereas we report the values for the 1:1 complex. Recently Singh and Banks³

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4108.

3. *Ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 6159.

4. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **15**, 125.

have determined the stability constant of the 1:1 complex at 0.1 ionic strength by spectrophotometry and pH-titration method. They represented the stability constant in the form:

$$K'' = \frac{[MR]}{[M][R]}$$

where R stands for

Our mean value of 0.470 for $K [H^+]$ at 0.1 ionic strength from our results at pH 4.0 and 4.5, when presented in the above form, provides a value of 11.68 for $\log K''$ in good agreement with 11.71 of Meek and Banks².

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